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Quality of Open University Education as an Entry Point for Sustainable Development in Egypt Between Reality and Hope

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Abstract

Education is generally regarded as one of the most important issues that has been unanimously held by the national consensus on its role and the need to develop it, and to increase its efficiency. In an effort to overcome this gap, reduce internal and external problems and risks and threats faced by the development of education in general and its active contribution to sustainable development, we try to clarify the role of the development of open university education and the achievement of quality standards in Egyptian universities as an essential input to sustainable development. The study aims to identify the quality of open university education as an input to Egypt's sustainable development between reality and hope. The researcher concluded the need to ensure the quality of education in general is urgent for the development of higher education if we are to achieve sustainable and inclusive development in all journals. and that the Foundation's vision, mission and objectives, curriculum design, teaching methods, learning resources and student services should be reviewed, The formulation of flexible long-term plans capable of graduating a good citizen capable of adapting to subsequent changes in society (A high-quality graduate in line with the requirements of the labour market locally and globally), and the need to regulate quality standards is essential for achieving sustainable, inclusive political, economic, social and cultural development. The researcher recommends that ensuring the quality of higher education is the key to achieving a society's sustainable economic, political, social, environmental and technological development.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Accreditation, Open Learning, Sustainable Development

Introduction

Education is generally regarded as one of the most important issues that has won national consensus on its role and the need to develop it. Education is responsible for the construction of the Egyptian human being and is able to cope with today's data. And with today's rapid changes and developments at the national and global levels, we have no choice but to build human beings as the means and purpose of development. Hence a qualitative shift in our Egyptian education. Has open education spread to Egyptian universities played a role in this shift or not? Does this type of education go beyond traditional pedagogical concepts and practices and take on new heights with modern concepts that have come to impose themselves on societies and through which the developed world works?

Egypt's political leadership has paid attention to the issue of the development of quality education and the needs of the labour market for certain types of education that enable the graduate to keep abreast of rapid developments in society. The issue of education in Egypt is an important priority for building Egyptian society.

Education and scientific research are the main and only challenge to overcoming the scientific and informatics gap between third world countries and developed countries (20).

Egypt has taken many steps towards achieving the quality of education since the adoption of the National Plan for the Development of Higher and University Education at the National Conference on Education in February 2000, followed by Ministerial Decision No. 1515 of 2001 establishing the National Committee for Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Higher Education. The National Commission for Quality Education and Accreditation was established by Act No. 82 of 2006, article 2 of which defines the Commission's educational institutions as follows: Universities, colleges, institutes and schools whatever their names are affiliated or supervised by the Ministry of Higher Education, Education, Al-Azhar Al-Sharif or other governmental or non-governmental.

The quality of education has had a direct impact on economic, social, political, cultural, environmental and technological systems, so you see (Zainab Abdel Nabi, 2016, 163-164) that open university education systems are one of the important educational innovations

that have received the attention of those involved in the educational process, through which the steady increase in those wishing to attend university education whose conditions do not enable them to attend school can be countered. Open education is a flexible system that allows students to learn according to their choice of time and place of study, in accordance with its ability and speed of learning at the lowest possible cost, and in a more flexible and freer framework than traditional systems.

He also notes (Ramadan Hussein, 66, 2010) that open education is a milestone in the transformation of forms of education and the transformation of the vision of contemporary universities from community educational institutions to civic organizations to circulate knowledge regionally and globally through research and study, hence open education is an added value for university education.

Fathi Abdul Rasoul, 2014, 7, emphasizes the role of the University, which represents the intellectual leadership entrusted with solving the problems and challenges of society, and is one of the most prominent institutions directly related to sustainable development in all its fields.

Zainab Abdulnabi, 164, 2016 (Farouk al-Bohi, 2014, 109) also emphasizes the role of education in sustainable development. Its achievement needs human forces capable of taking responsibility. education ", which requires relying on modern methods of education to equip them with the knowledge necessary for sustainability, University education is therefore responsible for achieving sustainable development requirements by preparing individuals for working life in society, and investing educational, research and service activities to develop and modernize society.

According to the researcher, the application of the open education system in Egypt has been significantly delayed; The researcher is likely to question its usefulness and effectiveness, and the limited availability of its requirements and possibilities for its application and success, but the evidence suggested that it could succeed provided it is well planned.

Study problem and questions:

Open university education has gone through many stages since its inception in the university year 1990/1991 until its cancellation in 2016 and its replacement with e-integrated education in 2017. In view of the achievements achieved 25 years after the implementation of this system, its limitations are shown to be below the expected and hoped level despite the novelty of the open university education system.

Zainab Abdulnabi, 2016, 165, noted that the current state of education is plagued by a crisis that has left open education unable to meet current and anticipated challenges, especially as new and accelerated challenges and changes emerge on the domestic and international scene, making open education incapable of achieving its desired mission and the required efficiency.

According to Wafa al-Mara 'i, 2006, 446-449, the actual reality of Egypt's open education system is highly problematic and affects its quality, as reflected in the limited success in open education due to: (Poor preparation of teaching staff to work in open education, with poor full knowledge of programme philosophy and objectives, methods and strategies used, and training in related techniques, to achieve their continued professional development in this area).

In order to overcome this gap and reduce internal and external problems, risks and threats faced by the development of education in general and its active contribution to sustainable development, we try to clarify the role of the development of open university education and the achievement of quality standards in Egyptian universities as an essential input to sustainable development by trying to answer the following questions:

1. What are the concepts of quality and accreditation, Egypt's experience in asserting quality and accreditation in education, open education and its quality, and sustainable development?
2. How does the quality of education as a variable affect Egypt's social, economic and political systems?
3. What is the role of open university education for sustainable development?

Objectives of the study

The study aims to identify the quality of open university education as an input to Egypt's sustainable development between reality and hope.

The importance of the study

Theoretical importance of the study:

- The quality of open university education is a tool for the development of society and the industry of its renaissance.
- Sustainable development has become a lifestyle imposed by the present era, characterized by accelerated and successive developments that have imposed themselves on Egyptian society.
- Limited studies associated with achieving the quality of open university education as an entry point for achieving sustainable development in Egypt.

Practical importance of the study:

- Developing practical scientific solutions applicable on the ground that contribute to the dissemination and upholding of a culture of quality in education as an important entry point for the development of the open education system for sustainable development.
- Using the results of this study to support the university's weaknesses and draw the attention of decision makers for development and development, in line with scientific and cognitive progress.

Study terms

Quality Assurance and Accreditation seen in Egypt as:

- Quality assurance: Quality fulfillment of all elements of the educational process from curricula, institutions, students, teachers, professors and various activities associated with the educational process.
- Accreditation: The National Authority for Quality Assurance of Education and Accreditation recognizes that the educational institution or programme meets a certain level of quality standards (standards - standards adopted) in accordance with the provisions of the law.

Standard criteria: They are the foundations set by the specialized committees with the participation of all relevant stakeholders and beneficiaries of the educational service guided by international standards while preserving the nation's cultural subjectivity and representing the minimum level of quality elements of educational institutions or programmes.

* The criteria adopted are determined by the educational institution for itself and adopted by the Commission on the condition that they do not fall short of the standards that are considered to be one of the strengths of the educational institution.

- Antony & Gnanam.2004,82 considers that ensuring the quality of traditional education is not sufficient to ensure the quality of open and distance education, while it considers that (National Quality Assurance Authority 2009, 145) that the quality of education is "The process of verifying that academic and institutional standards are compatible with the mission of the educational institution that has been defined, defined and achieved in accordance with the corresponding standards at the national and global levels. The quality of learning opportunities, scientific research, community participation and environmental development is appropriate and exceeds the expectations of all types of end beneficiaries of the educational institution's services."

- Open Learning (Open Learning) (Scholars, Jaber, 2013, 6) agreed that open education is an educational policy aimed at removing obstacles to learning by not requiring pre-qualifications for study, and by removing barriers to learning opportunities for persons with special needs, mandating the use of available technological means.

- While Zainab Abdulnabi 2016, 168, considers that open education must be mass education, accessible to all members of society, flexible and free in terms of the conditions of acceptance and teaching, Learning subject, time, place and range depending on students' needs, circumstances and requirements and is interested in helping the learner obtain the available science, training and expertise that helps him to be an active member of society, and a good citizen involved in the achievement of sustainable development.

Sustainable development

- Tre (Zainab Abdulnabi 2016, 169-170) that the term "sustainable development" is a relatively recent term and that this term received considerable impetus in the 1990s through interactive forums and international conferences. The International Organization for Education, Culture and Science (UNESCO) then deliberated on this term within its competencies and expanded its vision from an educational and educational perspective since the beginning of the third millennium.

- The researcher agrees with Iman Pepper 2003, 13 that sustainable development means reorienting resources and meeting first basic human needs such as literacy, and that the primary concern is to invest in human capital if we are to achieve sustainable development.

Study curriculum:

To achieve the study's objectives and answer its questions, and to verify the validity of its results, the researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum, by looking at the reality and quality of the open university education system in Egyptian universities as a key input for sustainable development, and to provide a set of findings and recommendations.

Some of the studies associated with the study's two themes:

Studies on the quality of open education (1:7) - Studies on education for sustainable development (8:11):

(1) The Sahar Abu Radi study (2015), entitled: "Envisage a proposal to ensure the quality of Egyptian university education in light of the introduction of strategic management", with a view to inform university education officials of the strategic management input, to overcome the problems facing open university education (educational - planning). The researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum.

(2) A charitable study, Masood (2013), entitled "Open University Learning and Distance Education", aimed at learning the concept of open university education and distance education in terms of justification, attributes, objectives, features, educational media for open university education and distance education. The researcher used the theoretical prescriptive curriculum. The researcher reviewed some models of open university and distance education institutions in the world such as: Arab Open University, United States Open University, Jerusalem Open University and Open University of Libya.

(3) The Wafa al-Sahari Study (2013), entitled: "Proposed educational conception for the development of open university education in Egypt in the light of contemporary variables", aimed at knowing what open education was and

the justification that led to it. The researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum.

(4) Amr Hassan (2013) study entitled: Quality Development with Open University Education at Cairo University, analytical study. The researcher used the descriptive curriculum. The study came up with a number of recommendations, the most important of which being the need for the Ministry of Higher Education to encourage and support open university education centres and provide guidance and training to quality committees in these centres.

(5) Mesim Fawzi Matir Al-Azam (2012) study entitled: Ensuring the quality and quality of open and distance education. The researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum. The study found a number of recommendations, the most important of which was the need to take the necessary action to recognize this pattern of education that graduates distinguished students as in traditional universities.

(6) The Ramadan Hussein working paper (2010) entitled: A different vision for open education in Egypt. The researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum. The study reviewed the precursors of the shift towards a different vision and its dimensions for open university education. The study concluded with guarantees of the effective application of this vision in open university education in Egypt.

(7) Mahmoud Akasha, Suhair Hawallah (2010) study entitled: Assessing the quality of open education in Egypt from the point of view of service providers and beneficiaries, with a view to detecting the factors that contributed to students' enrolment in the open education system. The researchers used the analytical prescriptive curriculum. The highest percentage enrolled in open education was due to the improvement of the social level, and the most contributing factor to improving the performance of Egypt's open university education system from the point of view of the study sample. The study recommended that civil society should recognize the academic factor granted by open education to its graduates.

(8) The Zainab Abdulnabi Ahmed study (2016) entitled: Ensuring the quality of open education as an entry point for achieving sustainable development requirements. The researcher used the analytical descriptive curriculum, and the study found: the proposed mechanisms to ensure the quality of open university education that meets the requirements of sustainable development.

(9) Nadia Brahimi study (2013), entitled "The role of UNU in human capital development for sustainable development", was a case study at the University of Mesaila. The researcher used the descriptive curriculum. The study concluded with a proposed conception of operationalizing the University's roles in human capital development from its three functions.

(10) Study of Baniya Nasr, Ahmed Sharaf (2013) entitled: "Development of academic programmes and curricula of the Faculty of Science of Sohag University in the light of standards of quality, accreditation and sustainable development" The study examined the experience of the Faculty of Science at Sohag University in improving the

faculty's outcomes from education, scientific research and community service. Having reviewed and developed academic programmes by building a system linking targeted learning outcomes with the scientific content of courses and applications related to sustainable development with prescribed academic standards through participation in the Swedish Agency for International Development's (SIDA) Higher Education in Sustainable Development Programme, which positively reflected performance.

(11) Ahmad Mahmoud Mohamed Al-Zinfali (2010) study entitled: Strategic planning of university education to meet the requirements of sustainable development. The study aimed to develop a strategic plan for state university education, so that it can meet the requirements of sustainable development. The researcher used the system analysis curriculum and environmental analysis method.

Study Procedures:

I. The general framework of the study includes the presentation, problem and questions of the study, its objectives, relevance, terminology, scientific curriculum, studies related to the study's subject and study procedures.

The results of the study included answering the study's questions, in order to provide a set of findings and recommendations.

To answer the study's questions in relation to the first question, which states:

What are the concepts of quality and accreditation, Egypt's experience in asserting quality and accreditation, open education and quality, and sustainable development?

What are the concepts of quality and accreditation:

Quality in higher education is one of the means of improving and upgrading the quality of education in an era of globalization that can be described as an age of quality. Quality is no longer a dream that educational institutions seek, or an intellectual luxury that they have the right to take or leave. and has become an urgent necessity dictated by the rapid changes in the higher education sector throughout the world and the demands of contemporary life, It -- if we may speak -- represents the spirit of the educational institution.

- The vision of institutions and interested persons differed on the definition and concept of quality, for example:

- The UK Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (QAA) defined quality as: a method to describe all systems, resources and standards used by universities and education institutes to maintain and improve standards and quality, including (teaching, how students learn, scholarships, research, etc.).
- The concept of quality, according to the UNESCO Conference on Education held in Paris in October 1998: "Quality in higher education is a multidimensional concept that should encompass all the functions and activities of education (curricula, educational programmes, scientific research, students, buildings, facilities and tools, services to the community, in-house self-education and internationally recognized benchmarking).

2. Egypt's experience in assuring quality and accreditation in education:

Egypt has made a number of serious attempts to achieve quality and accreditation since February 2000 and after the National Conference for the Development of Higher Education approved the Strategic Plan for the Development of Higher Education, which was translated into 25 projects implemented in three phases, each phase in line with the State's five-year plan from 2002 to 2017. A number of ministerial decisions were issued in this regard. The facilitation committee was formed and the development projects management unit for higher education institutions in Egypt was formed. It was also agreed to focus on six projects as a priority during the first phase. The six projects were:

(FOEP, ETCP, FLDP, ICTP, QAAP and HEEPF).

Funding sources for these six projects have been managed with a loan from the World Bank offset by funding from the Egyptian side, and other sources such as the United States and British Aid Authority, the Gulf Arab Fund and the European Union, as well as funding from the Ford Foundation of the United States to prepare the self-study of a pilot group of colleges and to prepare and fund the detailed feasibility study for the establishment of a national quality assurance and accreditation authority.

With the aim of adopting the "National Authority for Quality Education and Accreditation", higher education institutions are accredited through two main areas (institutional capacity and educational effectiveness) and sixteen standards in line with international standards to ensure the quality of higher education in educational institutions in Egypt, namely:

I. AREA 1: INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY: It contains eight criteria, namely:

(Strategic planning, organizational structure, leadership and governance, credibility and ethics, administrative apparatus, financial and material resources, community participation and environmental development, institutional evaluation and quality management).

Second area: Educational effectiveness: It contains eight criteria, namely:

(Students and graduates, academic standards, curriculum/programs, education and learning and supporting facilities, faculty, scientific research and activities, postgraduate studies, and continuous evaluation of educational effectiveness).

3. Open quality education:

Egypt's open education system began with the beginning of the university year 1990/1991, specifically on 8/1/1991, in a serious attempt to develop and improve its performance in offering distinctive programs that meet the requirements of the labour market. Global developments in the field of distance education are consistent with the University's commitment to implement all decisions of the Supreme Council of Universities in this regard. and that at the end of the study the student should obtain a postgraduate degree from the university to which he is bound

At the beginning of the university year 1990/91, the open education system began in the universities "Alexandria, Cairo and Ain Shams". One of the conditions for admission to

this system was at least five years of GCSEs, or equivalent, for enrolment in its programmes.

In 2008, the requirement of five years of GCSEs was abolished in a number of remote provincial universities with insufficient access to higher education.

In 2011, media colleges stipulated that applicants to the open education system should be public high school recipients to be treated as graduates of government colleges and the equality of the two degrees.

In 2016, the Supreme Council of Universities finally adopted a decision to abolish open education after a series of discussions, because it did not achieve the objective for which it was established, to prevent the issuance of bachelor's or bachelor's degrees in the name of open education, and to consider it as a "professional or educational" certificate, obtained by the graduate at the end of his term of study, which is only a professional certificate in his field of specialization.

On 26 October 2017, the Supreme Council of Universities adopted the introduction of the open education system in its developed form as "integrated education" and rules and regulations for the new integrated education system, with the degree awarded by it becoming a vocational diploma, not a postgraduate degree, with four years of schooling.

- Was there a need for open education?

• Open education imposed itself in the last quarter of the twentieth century on Egyptian society as one of the effective alternatives capable of developing university education in its various aspects. There were many justifications for the need for it agreed by many references and researchers (Zainab Ahmed Abdel Nabi: 2016, 179, Wafa al-Sahari: 2013, 904, Hassan Shehta: 2009, 30, Atef Shashra, 2006, 6), among these justifications:

- Lifelong learning and economic development: To keep abreast of rapid cognitive developments in Egyptian society.
- Social justice and balanced access: it was hoped that open education would achieve the principle of equal educational opportunities.
- Cost-effective: It was hoped that open education would contribute to new learning opportunities that would meet the individual's and society's needs and thus achieve sustainable development.
- Providing learning opportunities: state-of-the-art teaching and learning methods.
- Zainab Ahmed Abdel Nabi adds: 2016, 179) Based on the foregoing, it is imperative that there is a kind of non-traditional education that helps achieve sustainable development in various fields, helps society to benefit from its human resources and fulfill its requirements of culture and community participation to live in a advanced cultural, civilization, economic and social level, hence the need for open university education.

What is the need for quality open education?

The quality of open university education is needed for several reasons, including: (Mahmoud Akasha, Suhair Hawala, former reference, 5, scholars, Jaber, former reference, 31): (high unemployment rates, limited equal educational

opportunities in remote areas and elsewhere, Open education programmes are limited to predominantly traditional curricula and poor use of educational and technological media and the lack of competent academic mentors for scholars, and the apparent ignorance of distance and open education strategies education ", which was the most important reason for the weakness of learning systems and the weak basic infrastructure for the delivery of modern education strategies There are many modern universities where Internet services are not available, for example) As sustainable development and its achievement through open university education is a real strength of society's cohesion through its policy and strategy, indicators were necessary to measure sustainable development, as underscored by the Millennium Development Summit of the United Nations.

So (Zainab Abdulnabi 2016:183, Reham Abd Al 2012:306) agrees that there are a number of areas to verify quality indicators in open university education are: The quality of the faculty (teacher) and its scientific qualification, the quality of the beneficiaries (learner). University students are at the centre of the educational process. Their academic level must be upgraded theoretically and practically, their personalities refined, the quality of the structure of the educational programmes and their curricula, the quality of the classrooms and the provision of digital services.

4. Sustainable development:

Education was the fourth goal of UNESCO's Sustainable Development Strategy, as stated in the report

UNESCO's global Education for All monitoring to monitor the realities of education in achieving sustainable development goals and the extent to which education targets are achieved within the new framework of sustainable development goals.

- According to the report, from 2000 to 2015, significant progress had been made towards achieving the Millennium Development Goals for all, but by 2015, however, the goals set for education had not been achieved.

- In September 2015, United Nations Member States formally adopted in New York at their Conference on Sustainable Development and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which includes seventeen goals, including a new global goal in education, "Ensuring quality, equitable and inclusive education for all, promoting lifelong learning for all", coupled with seven goals and three means of implementation.

- I. The seven goals are:

Ensure that all boys and girls have free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education, leading to adequate and effective educational outcomes by the year 2030.

Ensure that all boys and girls have access to quality early childhood development, care and pre-primary education so that they are ready for primary education by 2030.

Ensure equal access for all women and men to quality and affordable technical, vocational and higher education, including university education, by 2030.

A significant increase in the number of young people and adults with appropriate skills, including technical and

professional skills for employment and decent jobs, and for entrepreneurship by 2030.

Eliminate gender disparity in education and ensure equal access to all levels of education and vocational training for vulnerable groups, including persons with disabilities and indigenous peoples, and children in vulnerable situations by 2030.

Ensure that all young people and a large proportion of adults, both men and women, are literate and numbered by 2030.

Ensure that all scholars acquire knowledge and skills to support sustainable development, including through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace, non-violence and global citizenship, appreciation of cultural diversity and appreciation of culture's contribution to sustainable development by 2030.

The three means of implementation are:

1- Build gender-sensitive, disabled and children's educational facilities, upgrade existing educational facilities and create an effective, safe and non-violent learning environment for all.

2- A significant increase in the number of scholarships available to developing countries globally, in particular to least developed countries, small island developing States and African countries, for higher education, including vocational training and information and communications technology grants, and technical, engineering and scientific programmes in developed and other developing countries by 2030.

3- A significant increase in the number of qualified teachers, through international cooperation for teacher training in developing countries, particularly in least developed countries and small island developing States by 2030. (22)

Previously, United Nations programmes, UNESCO, the Millennium Development Goals and Education for All emphasize the importance of education for sustainable development in an effort to alleviate poverty and improve health, all of which see education as an important means of achieving these goals (UNECSCO, 2005.7).

To answer the second question:

- How does the quality of education as a variable affect Egypt's social, economic and political systems?
- Societies' wealth is measured not only by their natural and material resources, but also by human resources, because the human element is the foundation of development and is the maker of the renaissance and development of society; Therefore, the success of economic, social, political, environmental and technological development policies that deal with the positive and negative impacts of change drivers such as poverty, food, urbanization, energy and others depends on the good exploitation and investment of the human component in society. and the phenomenon of underdevelopment of societies is often attributable to the inability of the human element with the necessary knowledge, Adequate attention, competence, positive attitudes, skills and capabilities development and investment

in solving problems and constraints related to society's development dimensions.

- This is why the researcher emphasizes the importance of the human element and its central role in the development process of societies; Egypt's quality and accreditation system recognized the existence of a standard specific to the administrative aspect, one with material and human resources as well as the standard of community participation and community development.

- Hence the great interest in education in general and higher education in its quality in particular because it is a source of human energy and an active element in social, economic, political, environmental and technological development. and, if human development is the process of developing the skills, knowledge and abilities of the human race, The natural place to achieve these characteristics is the educational system. The higher the quality and quality of education and the more successful it is in gaining these characteristics and characteristics, the higher the level of human development, Move the economic, social, political, environmental and technological movement forward, thereby achieving the goals of sustainable development.

- The researcher also stresses the importance of the quality of higher education in completing the process of sustainable and inclusive development in societies by graduating cadres capable of keeping abreast of the labour market and the political, economic, social and cultural changes facing the Arab nation. Hence, the need for sustainable professional development for all members of educational institutions and their employees at all levels and specializations.

- Many field studies have demonstrated a strong relationship between the quality of education and development indicators This has been the focus of most developed countries that have begun to develop their quality of education to ensure effective human development capable of achieving their national objectives and in line with the nature and needs of the labour market. Egypt is one of the countries that has begun to focus on ensuring the quality of higher education in conjunction with the development of general education. Within the framework of the directives and policies of the Egyptian Government, by focusing on the development of children's creativity and innovation and the development of their educational systems in line with strategic planning and the comprehensive national policy that seeks to achieve an advanced level in the world, Emphasizing the importance of obtaining effective educational outcomes and positive characteristics of individuals through the education system and the development of the individual as an irreplaceable human capital as a force Active in achieving sustainable and inclusive development.

- The researcher believes that in order to achieve this, it is necessary to obtain an effective educational product from the education system at the pre-university level so that the system is complete from the basis and a graduate capable of coping with the changes that exist politically, economically, socially and culturally and the requirements of the labour

market locally and internationally in order to achieve sustainable and inclusive development of society.

- In the face of conflicts experienced by Arab States after the so-called Arab Spring revolutions and to the disappointment of the Arab States, as well as the existence of global changes and the application of the system of globalization among most countries and the provisions of the GATT Agreement. Finally, the coronavirus crisis has meant that the Arab world as a whole must be aware of the role of education in the advancement of societies and its role in the achievement of sustainable and inclusive development of society. By establishing an effective education quality system map and working towards their achievement and application and to be a flexible adjustable system in line with the organization's vision and mission, Educational programmes, curricula and curricula must be in line with the State's policy of achieving quality for the educational outlet, which is the cornerstone of the sustainable and inclusive development process.

- Hence the importance of quality in higher education institutions; Because they are responsible for graduating these cadres at a high level of quality capable of entering and becoming active in developed societies, as well as having the capacity to develop economic, social and cultural development plans in line with society's policy and capabilities; This is to build a national technological scientific base that is instrumental in stimulating economic, social and cultural development.

Hence, quality variables must be regulated in all educational institutions; To achieve its objective through effective sustainable and inclusive development events on the ground, whether political, economic, social or cultural, to advance our beloved Egypt.

To answer the third question: What is the role of open university education for sustainable development?

Zainab Abdulnabi, 2016, 189, noted that education for sustainable development is intended for lifelong education in order to gain values, knowledge and skills that help individuals find new solutions to social, economic and environmental problems, thanks to Harlem "Brundtland" in consolidating the concept of sustainable development and defining its major features as stated in our 1987 World Commission on Development and Environment Joint Future Report. which gave a definition of sustainable development as follows: "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs".

- Indicators of sustainable development:

Mohammed Qurin, 2008, noted that there are a number of key indicators of sustainable development, including:

1- Development is a process, not a situation, and thus persistent and escalating, reflecting the renewed and growing needs of society.

2- Development is a societal process in which all groups, sectors and groups must contribute, not limited to a specific group or one resource.

3- Development is a conscious process, not a random process, specific goals with a long-term strategy, phased objectives, plans and programmes.

4- Development is a process guided by a development will that is aware of and committed to achieving societal goals.

5- Development is linked to its social and political framework through motivation and encouragement, linking effort and reward, affirming one's community affiliation and applying the principle of participation in its broad sense.

The researcher agreed with Zainab Abdulnabi, 2016, 194, that the most important mechanisms proposed to ensure the quality of open education and meet the requirements of sustainable development are: (Establishment of a quality assurance unit in each university of academics and administrators with expertise and follow-up on their achievements, improvement and development of the quality of the faculty of quality teaching skills and scientific research, use of modern techniques in the field of education, dissemination of the culture of quality of open education, and alignment of the university's outputs to the needs of the labour market).

- I conclude with an important question; Can this theoretical study be used to develop open education in its new form, "e-integrated education", in the light of quality assurance and sustainable development in this Egyptian society; which has become in need of many of these studies, especially if associated with applied studies.

•Conclusions and recommendations.

I. Researcher's conclusions:

Ensuring the quality of education in general is an urgent need to develop higher education if we are to achieve sustainable and inclusive development in all journals.

2. The Foundation's vision, mission, objectives, curriculum design, teaching methods, learning resources and student services must be reconsidered, and the formulation of long-term, flexible plans capable of graduating a good citizen capable of adapting to subsequent changes in society (a high-quality graduate in line with the requirements of the labour market locally and globally).

Quality standards are essential for achieving sustainable, inclusive political, economic, social and cultural development. The researcher's recommendations: Ensuring the quality of higher education is the fundamental focus of a society's sustainable economic, political, social, environmental and technological development.

Ensuring the quality of higher education has become the only test capable of providing positive scientific solutions in the face of global challenges associated with the drivers of change such as poverty and food, growing population, urbanization and climate change by addressing existing problems and developing preventive measures to prevent future problems by graduating a high-level, efficient educational product that achieves sustainable development goals.

The only quality of higher education capable of charting the progress and advancement of societies, and the establishment of the modern State with its institutions and organs.

4. The need to establish clear mechanisms to link the implications of change in the higher education sector with the requirements of globalization, knowledge economy and community development, and the possibility of real investment in this area through quality assurance systems, and to achieve sustainable development goals in Egyptian society.

5. The need to continuously develop and modify quality assurance standards by reviewing the institution's vision,

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